

Trend and Pattern of Population Growth And Distribution in Panvel City : A Geographical Analysis

Dr. Uttam Gadhe (Corresponding Author)
Head Department of Geography
K.M.C. College, Khopoli
Email: uttambsp@gmail.com

Mrs. Asmita Thakur
Research scholar
Department of Geography
University of Mumbai
Email: asmita191183@gmail.com

ARTICLE DETAILS

Research Paper

Keywords:

Population growth, Panvel City, Geographical analysis, 3-year moving average, Least squares method

DOI :

10.5281/zenodo.14544923

ABSTRACT

The study investigates population growth in Panvel City, Raigarh district, Maharashtra, over the past ten decades, focusing on key demographic trends and influencing factors. Using census data, the study highlights significant expansion areas and employs two statistical methods to forecast future growth: the 3-year moving average and the least squares method. The moving average smooths out short-term fluctuations in population changes, while the least squares method fits a linear regression model to estimate long-term trends. Additionally, the research analyzes spatial disparities in population density and the sex ratio across different wards in the city. These insights aim to assist urban planners and policymakers in effectively managing future population growth, promoting sustainable development, and addressing challenges related to overpopulation, resource allocation, and environmental impacts.

Introduction

Over the past century, Panvel has transformed from a small rural settlement into a rapidly urbanizing city, largely driven by its strategic geographic location and infrastructural developments. In the early 1900s, Panvel was a modest town with a population sustained by agriculture, fishing, and trade due to its proximity to Panvel creek. Population growth during this period was gradual, with limited migration, as Panvel was largely isolated from major urban centers. However, after India's independence in 1947, the

town began to experience steady growth as industrialization spread in nearby Mumbai, drawing rural migrants seeking employment opportunities. Key infrastructural projects, such as the Panvel railway station and the National Highway (NH – 4), improve the town's connectivity and laid the foundation for more significant demographic shifts.

A major turning point came in the 1980s and 1990s when Panvel was incorporated into the Mumbai metropolitan region (MMR) and became a key gateway to Navi Mumbai, a planned city developed for congested Mumbai. This, combined with improved road and rail infrastructure, led to a surge in the population as people sought more affordable housing and better living conditions outside of Mumbai.

By the end of the 1990s, Panvel's population had risen dramatically. In the 21st century, the cities' growth accelerated due to large scale infrastructure projects such as the Mumbai-Pune expressway, positioning Panvel as a major transport hub. The real estate boom in the city attracted residents and investors, transforming the city's landscape with new residential and commercial projects. The announcement of Navi Mumbai international airport and the Mumbai Trans-Harbor Link has only fueled expectations of further population growth in the coming years, as these projects promise to enhance connectivity and economic opportunities. By the 2011 census, Panvel's population had surpassed 180,000, with recent estimates suggesting even faster growth. Panvel's demographic evolution reflects the broader trends of urbanization in India, where peripheral towns like Panvel are emerging as a key source of growth due to their geographic advantages, affordability, and proximity to major metropolitan areas.

Review of literature

Urbanization in Maharashtra, one of India's most populous states, has undergone rapid growth, primarily driven by infrastructure development, industrialization, and migration into cities like Mumbai, Pune, and Nagpur. Researchers like Sanjay D. Pagar highlight how better economic opportunities and improved transportation networks have contributed to regional imbalances and challenges such as inadequate housing, environmental concerns, and pressure on civic amenities. In Aurangabad, R. U. Kharat and P. A. Khadke's spatio-temporal analysis emphasizes the dynamic nature of population growth, influenced by migration and economic opportunities. Achin Chakraborty, in *Sustainable Urbanization in India*, critiques the 'structural inequalities that limit equitable urbanization, while M.M.P. Rana discusses the sustainability challenges posed by rapid, unplanned urbanization in Bangladesh, particularly in Dhaka, calling for better governance and policy reforms to ensure sustainable development.

Objectives

- To analyse the trends in population growth in Panvel City
- To study ward wise distribution of population of study region
- Identify patterns of population change in study region.

Study area

Panvel, a city located in the Raigad district of Maharashtra State, India. Panvel Municipal Council is the first council developed in British era, 25th August 1852 then it is upgraded to Panvel Municipal Corporation by inclusion of CIDCO colonies in October 2016. Panvel is stretched between 18^o59'19.61'' N latitude and 73^o06'36.47'' E longitude. It lies approximately 40 km East of Greater Mumbai. Panvel is located in Western Ghat ranges and surrounded by the mountain of Matheran to the east, Pen taluka to the west, Khalapur taluka to the south and Thane taluka to the north. This region experiences a hot and humid climate and average rainfall is 200 – 250 cm. Temperature varies from 22^o C to 36^o C. Secondary and tertiary activities are prime source of economy.

Source: Estimated by Authors based on data provided by Panvel Municipal Corporation

Total area of Panvel city is 12.17 km². According to the Census of India 2011, the population of Panvel city is divided into 38 wards. In 1981, the total number of wards was 25. Over time, the number of wards increased to 26 in 2001. In 1901, the total population of Panvel City was 10152, while in 1961 it was 18130. In 2001, it reached 104058, but in 2011, the population of the city increased up to 180020. Panvel's population growth has been significantly influenced by its geographical location and connectivity. Initially, the city had relatively low population density, being a primary and agrarian economy with a vast surrounding rural area. However, with the expansion of Mumbai as a metropolitan region and the development of new transportation networks such as the Mumbai-Pune express highway and suburban railway lines, Panvel has witnessed rapid urbanization.

Database and methodology

This study analyzes population growth using secondary data from the District Census Handbook of Raigad (2001-2011) and urban development reports. A combination of statistical methods is employed: the 3-Year Moving Average reveals long-term trends amid short-term fluctuations, the Least Squares method establishes a linear growth trend, and the Exponential Growth Model projects future growth based on historical rates. This comprehensive approach provides insights into Panvel's population dynamics, considering both spatial and statistical variations.

Decadal growth rate of urban population in Panvel City compare to Raigad district, Maharashtra and India:

The decader growth rate of the urban population in Panvel City compared to India, Maharashtra, and Raigad from 1901 to 2011 reveals several key trends. In the early 20th century, Panvel City experienced slow growth, similar to Raigad and in contrast to India and Maharashtra, which showed consistent increases. Notably, Panvel and Raigad both saw negative growth in 1911, with Panvel's population declining by 33.44%, like lead due to rural-urban migration patterns or local socio-economic challenges. In the following decades, Panvel's growth picked up modestly, but it remained below national and state levels.

Table 1: Decadal growth of urban population (1901 – 2011)

Sr.No.	Year	India Growth Rate	Maharashtra Growth Rate	Raigad Growth Rate	Panvel City Growth Rate
1	1901	-	-	-	-
2	1911	0.35	0.99	-47.8	-33.44
3	1921	8.29	18.71	39.5	15.98
4	1931	19.12	15.56	7.7	6.75
5	1941	31.95	27.1	14.0	31.01
6	1951	40.52	62.42	50.73	35.59
7	1961	26.32	21.32	11.19	22.00
8	1971	38.30	40.74	43.03	46.73

9	1981	46.42	39.99	37.54	39.36
10	1991	36.29	39.09	56.6	58.73
11	2001	32.32	34.09	62.7	76.83
12	2011	29.68	31.72	81.40	73.00

Source : Census of India 2011, Maharashtra, Series-28, Part XII-B, District Census Handbook, Raigarh.

Note: Decadal growth given in percentage

The mid-20th century marks a turning point for Panvel City. From 1951 onwards, the city experienced a significant boom, mirroring Raigad but far outpacing both India and Maharashtra. By 1971, the panvels growth rate surged to 46.73%, a notable contrast to the national (38.30%) and state averages. This accelerated urbanization in Panvel is attributed to its growing importance as a transportation and industrial hub, benefiting from its proximity to Mumbai.

In the late 20th century, while India and Maharashtra's growth rates began to stabilize in the 1980s and 1990s, Panvel City continued its rapid expansion. In 2001, Panvel's urban population growth reached an

astounding 76.83%; subsequently, the growth rate was Raigad (62.7%), Maharashtra (34.09%), and India (32.32%). This period reflects Panvel's increasing role in the Mumbai metropolitan region's development.

By 2011, Panvel City maintained its high growth rate at 73%, even as the rates for India (29.68%) and Maharashtra (31.72%) continued to decline. This indicates that Panvel, unlike the broader trends of slowing urban growth in India and Maharashtra, remains a key area of rapid urbanization, likely driven by infrastructure development and its strategic location near Mumbai. Overall, Pune's urban growth has consistently outperformed that of Raigad, Maharashtra, and India, especially since the mid-20th century, highlighting its emergence as a significant urban center in the region.

Absolute Population growth in Panvel City since 1901 to 2011:

The population growth of Panvel City from 1901 to 2011 shows significant variation across the decades. In 1901, the population was recorded at 10,152. However, the city witnessed a sharp decline by 1911, with a reduction of 3,395 people, representing a decadal growth rate of -33.44%. The next decade saw a reversal of this trend, as the population grew by 1,080 people (15.98%) in 1921.

From 1951 onward, the population began to grow at a faster pace, reaching 14,861 in 1951 and 18,130 by 1961. The decader growth rate in the period fluctuated, with a notable spike from 1971 to 1991 when the population surged from 26,602 to 58,845, recording decadal growth rates as high as 58.73%.

Table 2: growth of population in Panvel City (1901 to 2011)

Sr.No.	Year	Total Population	Absolute Growth	Decadal Growth Rate
1	1901	10152	-	-
2	1911	6757	-3395	-33.44
3	1921	7837	1080	15.98
4	1931	8366	529	6.75
5	1941	10960	2594	31.01
6	1951	14861	3901	35.59
7	1961	18130	3269	22.00
8	1971	26602	8472	46.73

9	1981	37073	10471	39.36
10	1991	58845	21772	58.73
11	2001	104058	45213	76.83
12	2011	180020	75962	73.00

Source : Census of India 2011,Maharashtra, Series-28,Part XII-B,District Census Handbook, Raigarh.

Note : Decadal growth rate is given in percentage.

The above graph clearly shows the most dramatic increase occurred between 1991 and 2011. In this period, the population more than doubled from 58,845 in 1991 to 180,020 in 2011. The highest decided growth rate was observed between 2001 and 2011, at 73%, with an absolute increase of 75,962 people. These analyses highlight Panvel’s rapid urbanization and growth, especially after 1971, reflecting both natural population growth and migration into the city, likely driven by economic development and infrastructure expansion in the region.

The exponential graph of Panvel City’s population growth from 1901 to 2011 shows a clear exponential trend. In the early decades of the 20th century, the population remained relatively stable, with slight fluctuations between 1901 and 1941. After 1941, the population starts to increase at a notable pace, which accelerates significantly after 1971.

This sharp growth from 1971 onwards indicates a period of rapid urbanization and development in Panvel. Particularly striking is the steep curve between 1991 and 2011, where the population more than triples, reflecting intense migration and infrastructure expansion during this period. The exponential nature of the graph suggests that economic opportunities and urban planning likely played a crucial role in driving this population boom.

Overall, this graph illustrates how Panvel transformed from a small town into a rapidly growing urban center, with a sharp increase in population starting in the latter half of the 20th century, aligning with broader trends of urbanization in India.

Ward wise population distribution of Panvel City:

The ward-wise population distribution in Panvel City between 2001 and 2011 reveals significant population growth and demographic changes across the wards.

Table 3 :Ward wise Population Distribution Of Panvel City (2001 and 2011)

Ward No.	Population 2001	Population 2011	Ward No.	Population 2001	Population 2011
1	3442	7687	20	4265	2504
2	19963	13223	21	2433	2708
3	3259	7901	22	2051	2636
4	3274	15612	23	3826	3171
5	5903	15321	24	3445	2781
6	1963	3678	25	4639	2730
7	3881	2353	26	3195	4906
8	3878	2804	27	-	3227
9	3642	5818	28	-	3014
10	3535	2797	29	-	3234
11	3710	5148	30	-	2770
12	2263	5764	31	-	4643
13	2930	2516	32	-	2608
14	2612	4745	33	-	4839
15	2326	4212	34	-	3199
16	3149	2784	35	-	4348
17	2227	3129	36	-	2767
18	5556	2431	37	-	4633
19	2691	2584	38	-	8795
Total Population				104058	180020

Source : Census of India 2001 & 2011, Maharashtra, Series-28, Part XII-B, District Census Handbook, Raigarh.

In 2001, Panvel's total population was 104,058, spread across 26 wards. Among these, Ward 2 had the highest population at 19,963, followed by Ward 5 with 5,903. Several words had relatively lower

populations, with Ward 6 housing only 1,963 people. The population distribution appeared varied, with some wards like Wards 3, 4, and 9 showing populations in the range of 3,200 to 3,600, while others, such as Wards 15, 12, and 19, had lower figures, ranging between 2,000 and 2,600.

By 2011, Panvel's population had grown dramatically to 180,020, spread across 38 wards, indicating the city's rapid urbanization and expansion. The new wards created reflect the significant rise in population. Ward 4 saw one of the most dramatic increases, growing from 3,274 in 2001 to 15,612 in 2011. Similarly, Ward 5 grew to 15,321, and Wars 3 from 3,259 to 7,901. In contrast, Ward 2, which had the highest population in 2001, saw a decrease to 13,223 in 2011, possibly due to the division of its area into additional wards. Ward 38, newly created, reported a population of 8,795, the largest among the new wards.

The rapid increase in population across nearly all wards is a reflection of Panvel's growing role as an urban center. Wards such as 1,5 and 9, which were relatively populated in 2001, continued to grow significantly by 2011. While previously smaller wards such as 4 and 7 saw dramatic spikes in their populations.

Ward-wise population distribution (2001 and 2011)

Sr. No.	Population Size	2001 (Wards)	2011 (Wards)
1	Below 3000	6, 12,13,14, 15,17,19, 21,22 Total no. wards : 9	7,8,10,13,16,18,19,20,21,22, 24,25,30,32,36 Total no. wards : 15
2	3000 – 6000	1,3,4,5,7,8,9,10,11,16, 18,20,23,24,25,26 Total no. wards : 16	6,9,11,12,14,15,17,23,26,27, 28,29,31,33,34,35,37 Total no. wards : 17
3	6000 – 9000	-----	1,3,38 Total no. wards : 3
4	Above 9000	2 Total no. wards : 1	2,4,5 Total no. wards : 3

Between 2001 and 2011, the population distribution across various wards underwent significant changes. In 2001, there were nine wards with a population below 3000, but in 2011, this number had increased to 15, indicating either a population decline in a certain area or a wider dispersal of people

across more wards. Some wards, like 13, 19, 21, and 22, consistently remained in this category, while new wards such as 7, 8, and 10 joined, suggesting slower growth in these regions.

For the population range between 3000 and 6000, the number of wards slightly increased from 16 in 2001 to 17 in 2011. This reflects modest population growth in several wards like 27, 28, and 29 that emerged, showing a redistribution of population to these areas.

A new category for populations between 6000 and 9000 appeared in 2011, adding three wards (1, 3, and 38). This highlights notable growth in previously low-populated wards. Ward 1 and ward 3 transitioned from the 3000-6000 category, while ward 38, not listed in 2001, also entered this range, likely due to new development or population influxes.

Additionally, the number of wards with populations exceeding 9000 increased from just 1 in 2001 to 3 in 2011. Ward 2, which was the only 1 above 9000 in 2001, retained its high population; Ward 4 and 5 also joined this category, reflecting substantial population growth due to urban expansion or concentrated residential development. Overall, the data reflects a combination of population dispersal in some areas and significant growth in others.

Population Density:

Table 4: Population density of Panvel City (1961 to 2011)

Sr.No.	Year	Population	Area (sq.km.)	Population Density (per sq.km.)
1	1961	18130	12.15	1492
2	1971	26602	12.15	2189
3	1981	37073	12.15	3051
4	1991	58845	12.15	4843
5	2001	104058	12.17	8550
6	2011	180020	12.17	14792

Source : Census of India 2011, Maharashtra, Series-28, Part XII-B, District Census Handbook, Raigarh.

The population density of Panvel City has seen a significant increase from 1961 to 2011, reflecting rapid urban growth and development over the decades. In 1961, the population of Panvel was 18,130, with a density of 1,492 people per square kilometer, across an area of 12.15 square kilometers. Over the next decade, the population grew to 26,602 in 1971, raising the density to 2,189 people per square kilometer.

In 1981, the population reached 37,073, with a density of 3,051 people per square kilometer, marking steady growth. The next major jump occurred in 1991, when the population increased to 58,845, nearly doubling the density to 4,843 people per square kilometer.

In 2001, Panvel’s population had surged to 104,058, with a density of 8,550 people per square kilometer, as urbanization intensified. By 2011, the population had almost doubled again to 180,020, pushing the population density to 14,792 people per square kilometer. This trend reflects the rapid urbanization and migration into Panvel, transforming it from a small town into a densely populated city over the span of 5 digits.

Population of Panvel city and sex ratio

Table 5: Population and sex ratio of Panvel City (1901-2011)

Sr.No.	Year	Population	Male	Female	Sex ratio (per thousand)
1	1901	10152	5167	4985	965
2	1911	6757	3436	3321	967
3	1921	7837	4045	3792	937
4	1931	8366	4456	3910	877
5	1941	10960	5695	5265	924
6	1951	14861	7948	6913	870
7	1961	18130	9528	8602	903

8	1971	26602	13996	12606	901
9	1981	37073	19550	17523	896
10	1991	58845	30812	28033	910
11	2001	104058	54963	49095	893
12	2011	180020	92484	87536	946

Source : Census of India 2011, Maharashtra, Series-28, Part XII-B, District Census Handbook, Raigarh.

From 1901 to 2011, Panvel City experienced significant changes in its sex ratio. The sex ratio, which measures the number of females per 1000 males, fluctuated over the years. In 1901, the ratio was 965, meaning there was 965 females for every 1000 males. However, from 1931 to 1951, the sex ratio dropped significantly, reaching its lowest point in 1951 at 870, indicating a considerable gender imbalance.

Over time, the sex ratio gradually improved, rising to 946 in 2011, suggesting a more balanced distribution between males and females. This overall trend reflects both social and demographic changes in Panvel City during the period.

Analysis

Panvel City’s population data from 1901 to 2011, combined with insights from the accompanying graph, reveals a compelling narrative of growth and urbanization.

The 3-yearly moving average method:

Year	Population	3 yearly Moving Total	3 Yearly Moving Average
1901	10152	-	-
1911	6757	$10152 + 6757 + 7837 = 24746$	8249
1921	7837	$6757 + 7838 + 8366 = 22961$	7654

1931	8366	$7838 + 8366 + 10960 = 27164$	9055
------	------	-------------------------------	------

1941	10960	$8366 + 10960 + 14861 = 34187$	11396
1951	14861	$10960 + 14861 + 18130 = 43951$	14650
1961	18130	$14861 + 18130 + 26602 = 59593$	19864
1971	26602	$18130 + 26602 + 37073 = 81805$	27268
1981	37073	$26602 + 37073 + 58845 = 122520$	40840
1991	58845	$37073 + 58845 + 104058 = 199976$	66659
2001	104058	$58845 + 104058 + 180020 = 342923$	114308
2011	180020	-	-

From 1901 to 1931, Panvel's population saw relatively moderate growth, with the 3-yearly moving average rising from 8,249 in 1911 to 9,055 in 1931. The first significant surge occurred between 1931 and 1941, as the moving average jumped to 11,396, reflecting a notable population increase during this period.

The post-World War II era saw continued growth, particularly after 1951, when the moving average rose to 14,650. This graph shows what trend exhilarated for the period between 1961 and 1981, as the moving average climbed from 19,864 in 1961 to 40,840 in 1981, making a period of rapid urbanization and expansion. The most dramatic increase occurred between 1981 and 2001, where the moving average nearly tripled, reaching 114,308 by 2001. This share price underscoring the massive urban development and population boom during this time. By 2011, the city's population continued to grow.

The graph depicting Panvel City’s population alongside its 3-yearly moving average from 191 to 2011 reveals several significant trends. Initially from 1901 to 1951, the population exhibited steady but moderate growth, with the moving average indicating a consistent upward trend during this period. However, notable acceleration in growth occurred after 1951, particularly between 1961 and 1981, when pen organization began to take off, leading to a sharper increase in both the population and the moving average. The most dramatic surge transpired between 1981 and 2011, as the population skyrocketed from approximately 37,000 to 180,000. These steep rises in the moving average underscoring a phase of intense development and urban migration, likely tree one by industrialization and improvements in infrastructure. Overall, the data illustrate Panvel’s transformation from a modest town to a rapidly expanding urban center, particularly evident in the significant growth trend after 1981.

The Method of Least Squares Regression

The least regression statistical method is used to predict future populations based on past data. By applying the least squares method, we derive the linear equation, which is used to project future populations assuming the trend continues. To perform a method of least squares regression analysis on population data, first need to calculate the coefficients of the linear equation.

The linear trend equation is given by:

$$Y = a + bx$$

Where:

- Y is the dependent variable (population in this case)
- X is the independent variable (years represented as X)
- a is the y-intercept
- b is the slope of the line

Method of Least Square

Year	Population(Y)	X	X ²	XY	Trend Values
1901	10152	-11	121	-111672	-23061.08
1911	6757	-9	81	-60813	-11539.96
1921	7837	-7	49	-54859	-18.84
1931	8366	-5	25	-41830	11502.28
1941	10960	-3	9	-32880	23023.4
1951	14861	-1	1	-14861	34544.52
1961	18130	1	1	18130	46065.64
1971	26602	3	9	79806	57586.76
1981	37073	5	25	185365	69107.88
1991	58845	7	49	411915	80629
2001	104058	9	81	936522	92150.12

2011	180020	11	121	1980220	103671.24
	483661		572	3295043	

The two normal equations for calculating b and a are given by :

$$\sum Y = na + b \sum X$$

$$\sum XY = a \sum X + b \sum X^2$$

Where :

- n is the number of observations.
- $\sum XY$ is the some of the products of X and Y
- $\sum X$ is the sum of X.
- $\sum Y$ is the sum of Y
- $\sum X^2$ is the sum of squares of X

After the putting values in above formulas the final values are :

$$a = 40305.08$$

$$b = 5760.56$$

the linear Trend equation : $Y = a + bx$

$$Y = 40305.08 + 5760.56X$$

Interpretation of the equation

intercept (a): the y-intercept (a=40305.08) indicates the estimated population when X=0 (which corresponds to the year 1901). This is essentially a baseline figure for the population at that point in time.

Slope(b): the slope (b = 5760.56) indicates that for each unit increase in X (each decade from 1901 onward), the population is expected to increase by approximately 5760.56 people. They show the rate of growth over the observed years.

The graph shows a straight, upward-sloping line (shown in orange), highlighting a study and predictable growth in population over time. population growing by approximately 5,760 people every 10 years. The positive slope reflects the fact that as time progresses, the population continues to rise at a relatively constant rate. This linear trend suggests regular, non-volatile population expansion, which aligns with historical growth patterns seen in many regions during industrialization and modernization phases. The consistency of the slope indicates no drastic accelerations or decelerations in population growth over the analyzed period.

Conclusion

Panvel City has experienced significant population growth over the decades, particularly from the late 20th century onward. Initially facing challenges with a negative growth rate in the early 1900s, the city saw a marked increase after 1951, especially in the 1970s with a growth rate of 46.73%. The 1990s were pivotal, with rates picking at 58.73% in 1991 and 76.83% in 2001. By 2011, the growth rate remained strong at 73.00%, underscoring Panvel’s transformation into a vital urban center.

Considering the population growth rate over the time, the population surged notably from 58,845 in 1991 to 104,058 in 2001, reflecting a decadal growth rate of this trend continued into 2011, with the population reaching 180,020 and a growth rate of 73%.

The population distribution across the wards in Panvel City shows significant growth from 26 wards in 2001 to 38 wards in 2011. In 2001, the total population was 104,058, distributed in 26 wards, with ward 2 having the highest population at 19,963, while ward 6 had the lowest at 1,963. By 2011, the total population increased to 180,020, distributed in 38 wards, with Ward 4 emerging as the most populated at 15,612, and Ward 7 the least at 2,353.

Over the period, population density soared from 1,492 to 14,792 people per square kilometer, reflecting rapid organization and growing demand for housing and services. The area remained relatively constant at around 12.15 to 12.17 square kilometers.

In terms of sex ratio, initially it was relatively stable, hovering around 965 in 1901 but declining to a low of 870 in 1951. However, gradual improvement occurred in subsequent decades, culminating in a sex ratio of 946 by 2011.

Panvel city has experienced significant population growth due to its proximity to Mumbai, improved infrastructure, nodal railway junction, proposed airport, low prices of housing and land compared to Mumbai, rapid urbanization, and increased economic opportunities. However, this rapid growth presents several drawbacks, including overcrowding, environmental degradation, traffic congestion, and pressure on public services like education and healthcare. To address these challenges, future development should focus on sustainable urban planning that prioritizes green spaces and efficient land use. Enhancing public transportation can reduce traffic congestion and promote eco-friendly commuting, while continuous investment in infrastructure is essential to accommodate the growing population. Additionally, involving local communities in planning processes ensures that development meets residents' needs and fosters social cohesion. Implementing environmental conservation initiatives will also help mitigate the negative impacts of urban growth, ultimately enhancing the quality of life for the city's residents.

References

- Bhagat, R. B. & Jones, G. W., 2016. Demographic Dynamics Of Mega- Urban Regions : The Case Of Mumbai. ResearchGate.
- Chakraborty, A., n.d. Structural Limits to Equitable Urbanization. In: J. Mukherjee, ed. Sustainable Urbanization In India. Kolkatta: Springer, pp. 41-52.

Deore, S. U., 2014. Analysis Of Population Growth and City Expansion using Census, Topographical and Remote Sensing Data : A Case Study of Nashik City of Maharashtra (India). Online International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, IV(I), pp. 326-332.

Ghadge, A. K. & Patil, B. S., 2023. An Impact of Migration on Urbanization Trends in Navi Mumbai : Socio-Economic Perspective. Journal of Advanced Zoology, 44(S-8), pp. 87-91.

Kharat , R. U. & khadke, P. A., 2018. Spatio-Temporal Analysis Of Urban Population Growth And Distribution In Aurangabad City. International Journal of Research in Social Science, 8(3), pp. 428-440.

Khare, U., Thakur, P. & Joshi, P., 2020. Temporal Changes in Urban Population In Maharashtra State Using GIS. IOSR-JHSS, 25(10), pp. 01-09.

Pagar, S. D., 2015. Geographical study of growth and level of urbanization in Maharashtra State, India. Golden Research Thoughts, 5(1).

Rana, M. M. P., 2011. Urbanization and sustainability : challenges and strategies for sustainable urban development in Bangladesh. Springer, Issue 13, pp. 237-256.

Shaw, A., 1994. Urban Growth and land-use conflicts : The case of New Bombay. Bulletin Of Concerned Asian Scholars, 26(3), pp. 33-46.

Tripathi , A. & Gandhi, A., 2022. Analysis Of Land Use Land Cover Change and Relative Growth in Social Amenities : Panvel Tahsil, Maharashtra. IRJET, pp. 239-245.